

ANALYSIS OF TALL BUILDING USING ETABS WITH P-DELTA ANALYSIS

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under the guidance of

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ABSTRACT: As urbanization increases worldwide, the construction of tall buildings in seismic regions is becoming increasingly common. In heavily populated cities, the available land for buildings is becoming scarcer and scarcer, and the cost of land is becoming higher and higher. So, the high rise structures are proposed for residential and commercial purposes. They may be easily affected by seismic as well as wind loads, so the buildings get deformed and collapsed easily. To avoid these problems we consider p-delta effect in designing. As the number of stories increases p-delta effect becomes very important. The P-Δ effect is relevant in structural engineering problems, especially in civil engineering, where we're dealing with large structures with proportionally decreasing small moments of inertia as they continue to be extended in absolute height. In this study p-delta (P-Δ) effect on high-rise building is studied for the analysis of G+10 building and models were done by ETABS. Seismic and wind loads are applied to model and the displacements and storey drifts are compared for the structure with and without P-delta effect.

Keywords: p-delta effect (P-Δ), displacement, shear wall, ETABS.

I. INTRODUCTION

National Building Code (NBC) defines all buildings which are 15 m or above in height are considered as high-rise buildings. But many development authorities define a high-rise

building or a multi-Storied building as a building of a height of 24 meters or above.

When a slender structure is exposed to lateral loads i.e. wind or seismic loads it experiences sway or lateral displacement. Whenever this lateral displacement is increased to peak then gravity loads start to act with an eccentricity. This is equal to the magnitude of elastic deflection causing an additional overturning moment. Due to which, a second order deflection is developed in the structure. This second order effect caused in the structure is known as P-Delta effect. Where “P” is the gravity load and “Δ” is the displacement experienced through first order or elastic analysis for lateral forces. The P-Delta effect is shown in the Figure 1. Where the Δ₂ is second order deflection caused due to P-delta effect.

Figure 1: P-Delta Effects on a Simple Cantilever Column

The P-Δ effect is experienced in all structures when they were subjected to an axial load in combination with lateral displacement. The major effect is observed due to deflection of the structure as a whole and also termed as P-delta

(P- Δ). However, this research is done on the P-delta effect observed through structural instability (P- Δ). Tall structures and buildings with more number of stories will undergo large P-delta effect. They are to be designed with Proper recommended considerations. The importance of P-Delta non-linear analysis is continually increasing in high rise buildings are getting very popular and playing a key role.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of P-delta effect on a frame

II. OBJECTIVES OF WORK

- To perform linear static analysis of the tall structure by using E-TABS.
- To study the P-DELTA (non-linear) effect on tall structure by using ETABS and to study the effect of axial loading on the structure.
- To study the results of the structure, i.e. story drift and displacement with and without P-DELTA effect.

III. ANALYSING OF BUILDING AND MODELLING IN ETABS

A G+10 storey building with plan of 41x50 each storey height of 3m was analysed in ETABS by considering p-delta effect and without p-delta effect and the models were analysed .

Modelled steps in ETABS:

1. Preparing grid for layout
2. Assigning member properties of beams, columns, and slab and wall panels.
3. Preparing load cases like Dead, live, earthquake and wind loads.
4. Make load combinations and modal mass of the structure.
5. Assigning P-delta loads and the structure
6. Run the analysis
7. Note down the results.

The materials used for the analysis are M-25 for slabs and M-30 grade reinforced concrete for beams and columns and Fe-500 grade steel for the entire structure.

A Geometry of model: The analysis is carried out for G+10 storey building with reinforced concrete properties as specified above.

The model details are given below:

- Number of stories = G+ 10
- no. of Bays in x-direction= 6
- no. of Bays in y-direction= 8
- Height of each storey= 3m
- Slab depth= 125mm
- Size of the transverse beams= 300x500
- Size of the columns 900x900mm.
- zone= III
- Response reduction factor considered = 3
- Importance factor considered= 1

B. Load Proportions

i. Dead load (DL): The dead load is considered as per IS code book i.e. IS 875- 1987 part-I .

- Unit weight of concrete = 25KN/m³
- Floor finish =1KN/m³
- Roof finish = 1KN/m³

ii. Imposed load (LL): Imposed load is also known as live load, it is considered as per IS code book i.e. IS 875-1987 part-II.

- Live load of slab = 4KN/m³
- Live load on roof = 3 KN/m³

iii. Earthquake load:

The earthquake load is considered as per IS code book i.e. IS-1893-2002 PART-I and the factors considered are

- Response reduction factor considered = 3.0
- Zone factor considered= 0.16
- Importance factor considered= 1
- Damping = 5%
- Soil condition = medium.

C. linear static analysis and non-linear static analysis (p delta): The linear static & non-linear is carried out for G+10 storey building with P-delta(P-Δ) and without considering P-delta(P-Δ) in ETABS. From the analysis results, story drifts, displacements are obtained and these are compared.

IV. MODELS CONSIDER FOR ANALYSIS

A. Model

Figure 3 3D view

Figure – 3 shows the 3d model of the building considered for analysis

B. Story Data

Name	Height mm	Elevation mm	Master Story	Similar To	Splice Story
Story11	1000	31000	Yes	None	No
Story10	3000	30000	Yes	None	No
Story9	3000	27000	Yes	None	No
Story8	3000	24000	Yes	None	No
Story7	3000	21000	Yes	None	No
Story6	3000	18000	Yes	None	No
Story5	3000	15000	Yes	None	No
Story4	3000	12000	Yes	None	No
Story3	3000	9000	No	Story4	No
Story2	3000	6000	No	Story4	No
Story1	3000	3000	No	Story4	No
Base	0	0	No	None	No

Table 1: Story data

C. Load Pattern

Name	Type	Self Weight Multiplier	Auto Load
Dead	Dead	1	
Live	Live	0	
SDL	Superimposed Dead	0	
EQX	Seismic	0	IS1893 2002
EQY	Seismic	0	IS1893 2002
WIND X	Wind	0	Indian IS875:1987
WIND Y	Wind	0	Indian IS875:1987
WALL	Superimposed Dead	0	

Table 2: Load pattern

V. RESULT

A. Story Drift

Story number	Height of each story (m)	Story Drift without P Delta effect(mm)	Story Drift with P Delta effect(mm)
Story 11	1	0.000443	0.000864
Story 10	3	0.000363	0.000732
Story 9	3	0.000215	0.000658
Story 8	3	0.000201	0.000589
Story 7	3	0.000153	0.000523
Story 6	3	0.000132	0.000464
Story 5	3	0.000122	0.000414
Story 4	3	0.0001	0.000268
Story 3	3	0.0001	0.000235
Story 2	3	0.0001	0.000112
Story 1	3	0.000106	0.00001
Base	0	0	0

Table 3 : Story Drifts

B. Displacement

Story number	Height of each story (m)	Displacement without P Delta effect(mm)	Displacement with P Delta effect(mm)
Story 11	1	79.649	80.431
Story 10	3	70.359	73.445
Story 9	3	60.99	70.03
Story 8	3	51.631	61.23
Story 7	3	42.406	50.143
Story 6	3	33.485	40.32
Story 5	3	25.053	33.11
Story 4	3	17.406	20.456
Story 3	3	10.743	12.44
Story 2	3	5.41	6.31
Story 1	3	1.692	2.006
Base	0	0	0

Table 4 : Displacements

VI. CONCLUSION

The following results were concluded from the analysis

- The story drift increases with increase in story height.
- The displacement increases with increase in story height
- The story drift with P delta effect is greater than the story drift without P delta effect
- The displacement with P delta effect is greater than the displacement without P delta effect

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